

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF LEARNING MANY LANGUAGES AS A YOUNG CHILD

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Annotation: This article discusses the importance of learning multiple languages in childhood and learning foreign languages in human life.

Key words and phrases: foreign language, bilingualism, language acquisition, teacher, learner, visual aids.

At present, in connection with global geopolitical, economic and socio-cultural changes, more and more new demands are placed on people, the demands of modern production on the level of professional training of personnel are increasing. Thus, the need to communicate freely in a foreign language, and sometimes in several languages, increases. Life has changed, the way of receiving information has changed and its volume has changed significantly. So, now almost no one doubts the feasibility of learning foreign languages: in the modern world, learning them is useful and necessary [3, 134].

Learning foreign languages from childhood is very important. Because, along with the rapid reception of information, the child will also have a period of developing speech. It is not for nothing that they say that knowledge acquired in youth is a pattern carved in stone. For this reason, foreign language teaching is started in pre-school educational institutions, i.e. kindergarten and lessons are conducted based on the needs and interests of children. From the age of five months, the child begins to repeat the sounds around him and imitates what his mother says. From about the age of two, he begins to learn his mother tongue consciously. In a child, the development processes of language and thinking take place together. Between the ages of four and ten, a child can develop the ability to learn foreign languages. The most important thing is to follow the requirements of early learning of foreign languages to children of kindergarten age requires special attention and

responsibility. In other words, it is necessary to abandon the explanation of grammar rules and conduct lessons that are easy to learn and easy to understand, based on the child's world view and interest.

Of course, poems, songs, fairy tales and short stories in English and Russian with lots of pictures, cartoons with subtitles, and simple texts play an important role in this. The effect of using visual aids as much as possible is very great. In the process of teaching a foreign language, the child should be encouraged to speak as much as possible. Pronunciation is an important part of learning a foreign language. The use of technical means will give a good result in this. By repeatedly listening to spoken texts in a foreign language, the child remembers them and imitates them in oral speech. For example, the use of soundtracks, poems and songs from cartoons gives the child pleasure and is quickly preserved in his memory [8].

The importance of learning a foreign language:

Learning foreign languages from childhood makes our brain grow, not only in childhood, but also in adulthood. Research shows that regardless of how old we are, learning other languages demonstrates cognitive benefits. Bilingual people have bigger brains, better memory, creativity, problem solving, etc. These advantages make it easier not only to learn foreign languages, but also to learn everything. Traveling becomes easier and cheaper when you learn a foreign language. Of course, many people like to travel. Knowing the language will be of great benefit to us when we go to a foreign country. When we go in for a simple meal, we can easily explain the food we want. We can also ask for directions from the surrounding local people without any difficulties. If we were to take a guide with us, it would be very expensive, and this is proof of how important it is to learn and know a foreign language.

Learning foreign languages also opens the way to finding a job. More and more companies are operating in several, often dozens of countries around the world, but they cannot do this without hiring people who understand at least one foreign language. Even in small local companies, the ability to speak a second language is

likely to set us apart from other workers, and of course, it will allow us to make new friends while learning foreign languages. New faces, new worldviews, getting to know interesting people and becoming lifelong friends are definitely goals worth striving for. Learning foreign languages is a reliable way to speed up these processes. Language helps us to express our feelings, desires, and connect with new worldviews, new friends, and create meaningful relationships. Learning foreign languages encourages us to be more open-minded, learning a foreign language and becoming immersed in completely new cultures and worldviews is the surest way to become an open-minded, understanding, tolerant person and absolutely invaluable. Another important aspect of learning a foreign language is that it helps to better understand one's own language and culture. Learning a foreign language actually engages a person in reverse psychology and allows them to better understand their native language and culture. This is one of the most unexpected benefits of learning a foreign language. We become more aware not only of our cultural traditions, but also of the grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation of our first language. The benefits of learning multiple languages have the ability to adapt us to succeed in almost every aspect of our lives. Learning multiple languages is important and there are countless reasons to learn a foreign language. Learning a foreign language helps to overcome language barriers and connects people to a deeper level of mutual understanding.

With age, people do not face any obstacles in learning a foreign language, except for environmental factors. Therefore, it is still not too late, the importance and place of learning many languages in our life is very great [9].

References:

1. Dushatova, S. (2022). EVFEMIZM TUSHUNCHASI TAHLILI.
2. Dushatova, S. (2022). LINGUISTIC AND SOCIAL ORIGINATION OF TABOOS. Science and innovation, 1(B6), 318-321.

3. Dushatova, S., & Tursunaliyev, M. (2022). CHET TILLARINI O'RGANISHNING INSON RIVOJLANISHIGA TASIRI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(7), 133-138.
4. Dushatova, S., & Azamov, M. (2022, November). SO'Z TURKUMLARI TASNIFI. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 1, No. 6, pp. 89-95).
5. qizi Dushatova, S. B., & qizi Qodiraliyeva, N. I. (2022). EFFECTIVE METHODS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. *International Academic Research Journal Impact Factor 7.4*, 1(5), 63-67.
6. Shokhsanam, D., & Makhmudova, M. (2022). BENEFITS OF DAILY READING. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(8), 28-32.
7. Dushatova, S., & Burgutova, G. (2022). CHET TILLARINI BILISHNING FOYDALARI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(8), 40-45.
8. Turdaliyeva, D., Abbasova, N., & Hamidova, N. (2022). LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF MICROTTEXTS. *Science and Innovation*, 1(7), 1235-1239.
9. Гафуров, Б. З. ТЕКСТЫ С ФОНОСТИЛИСТИЧЕСКИМИ ФОНОВАРИАНТАМИ И ИХ ПЕРЕВОД (НА МАТЕРИАЛЕ УЗБЕКСКОГО ЯЗЫКА). *ILIM hám JÁMIYET*, 72.
10. Zakirovich, G. B. (2022). The Theme of Female Gender in the Texts of Advertising in Russian and Uzbek Languages (On the Material of Medical Vocabulary). *Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT*, 2(1), 23-29.
11. Gafurov, B. Z. (2022). Analysis of medical version in texts of advertising of hygiene products in the fight against COVID-19 (on the material of Russian and Uzbek languages). *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*.

12. Gafurov, B. Z. Similarities and differences of segment background options for Russian, Uzbek and English languages. *Monografia pokonferency jnascience, Research, development*, 26, 17-19.
13. Gafurov, B. Z. (2021). Medical terminology in advertising text. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 5(3), 30-40.
14. Zakirovich, G. B. (2020). Super-segment phonostylistics as the basis for studying the problems of accent variants of Russian nouns. *CREATION OF ETHNOGRAPHIES WITH POPULAR TRADITIONS*, 11(13), 39.
15. Gafurov, B. Z. (2021). Study of advertising texts in Russian on the topic of medical terminology. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies (IJPSAT).–Indonesia*, 26(1), 586-590.
16. Gafurov, B. Z. (2020). ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP OF MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY WITH SEGMENT PHONOSTYLISTICS OF THE NOUN IN RUSSIAN, UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (1), 464-466.